

Free Particle Quantum Mechanics from Inherent Force Related dt and dx Values?

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Newtonian mechanics is well known for shrinking $dx \rightarrow 0$ and $dt \rightarrow 0$ with $v = dx/dt$. We have suggested in previous notes that in nature there should exist fixed minimal dt_1 and dx_1 values, probably much smaller than typical tiny dx , dt values in the classical world. It would seem dt_1 and dx_1 might be related to a particular force, but in general we suggest that one might be able to fix maximum values for these from special relativity.

We have suggested the two sets dx, dt (with $dx/dt = v$) and dx_1, dt_1 in previous notes. A question which arises is: Why would these two sets not have appeared when special relativity was developed? In fact, special relativity seems biased towards $dx/dt = v$ because one considers physics in a rest frame (for a rest mass) and a frame moving with constant $-v$. In such a case, the Lorentz invariant $-Et + px$ (where t is measured from 0 and x from 0 as well such that these are intervals) is explicitly linked to $x/t = v$.

We have pointed out before that this Lorentz invariant should apply to any x, t sets as it is a mathematical value. If such other x_1, t_1 sets, however, have no physical relevance, one might ask: Why consider them? We suggest that the notion of a set dx_1, dt_1 such that $dx_1/dt_1 \neq v$ has a physical reason to exist and that dt_1 and dx_1 are independent of each other. We suggest that this is why one may consider $-E dt_1 + p dx_1$ such that $dt_1 = \text{constant}/E$ and $dx_1 = \text{constant}/p$. This independence then holds in any frame and the idea of E and p controlling the dt_1 and dx_1 values is reasonable because E and p are linked to m_0 and v (not to the particular force) and so one might suspect that dt_1 and dx_1 are also linked to E and p (i.e. the effects of the force enter through these) and that is really special relativity which creates dt_1 and dx_1 values. As we have argued before, if dt_1 and dx_1 values exist, then one cannot really track motion within these regions and so stochastic physics is used to describe what happens within dt_1 , dx_1 , namely interactions with a force. Thus, dx_1 is a maximum value for a spatial range of probabilistic impulse hits in x .

Newtonian Mechanics

Newtonian mechanics is based on $dx \rightarrow 0$ and $dt > 0$ such that

$$dx/dt = v \quad ((1))$$

There is no absolute dx minimum and dt minimum, but physically it seems reasonable that these (dt_1, dx_1) should exist (possibly force dependent) as we have argued in previous notes. The assumption of Newtonian mechanics is that one should ultimately consider force and that it changes momentum. In such a case, one is only interested in dx , dt linked to v as this is the observable, and not dx and dt . If a fixed dt_1 and dx_1 exist, then they too should be observable, not just changes in v . Both v and dx_1, dt_1 should be physical observables linked to interactions. If this is the case, then why are dx_1, dt_1 not observed in classical physics, while v is? We have argued in previous notes that it is because dx_1, dt_1 are too small to be seen on classical scales.

Conceptually, Newtonian mechanics is based on changes to v , i.e. $dp/dt = d/dt (mv) = m_0 dv/dt$ (usually) = Force. dt_1, dx_1 do not explicitly appear anywhere. This velocity-centric viewpoint is carried over to special relativity because one considers a rest mass m_0 at $x=0, t$ and considers the it seen by a frame moving with $-v$. In such a case, one has:

$$x'/t' = v \quad ((2))$$

From this velocity-centric view, one may create the Lorentz transformation and also the Lorentz invariant:

$$-Et' + px' \text{ such that } x'/t' = v \quad ((3))$$

t' and x' are intervals measured from $t'=0, x'=0$ and it seems that there are no other intervals present. Again, forces create changes in velocity and so velocity is the only measurable of interest and it is linked with dx, dt such that $dx/dt=v$. Even if a dt_1 and dx_1 exist, one might ask: Why would they be relevant? Certainly if they are tiny compared to small dx, dt values used in the system, one would not really be concerned about their existence. The problem is that nature should fix the values of dx_1 and dt_1 . Given that ((3)) is a general math expression, one may use any dt, dx intervals one wishes, including dt_1, dx_1 .

Physically, one expects dt_1, dx_1 to be independent of each other, which we suggest is a key idea. This leads to:

$$-Edt_1 + pdx_1 \rightarrow dt_1 = -\text{constant}/E \text{ and } dx_1 = \text{constant}/p \quad ((4))$$

E and p control the values of dx_1 and dt_1 and E and p are linked to the force which created them (as well as to m_0, v).

From photon considerations, $\text{constant} = \hbar$ which shows that dt_1 and dx_1 are tiny in the classical world. There are, however, time and length scales for which they are not. In such a case, one has dt_1, dx_1 regions which are appreciable with respect to the system length and interactions may occur within dt_1, dx_1 . Given the definition of dt_1, dx_1 , one cannot describe interactions in these regions deterministically and one may only consider probability. Given that repetition of these intervals, one requires a probability which respects these intervals, but otherwise has no bias.

One may create this probability using conservation of energy and momentum together with Lorentz invariance, as discussed in previous notes, i.e.

$$\exp(-iEt + ipx) \quad ((5))$$

One may also maximize entropy subject to an ipx probability constraint as also shown in a previous note. Here we argue that given that p is chosen as the a priori Lagrange multiplier, i.e.

$$1/(1/p) \quad ((6))$$

This means that one is considering a uniform distribution along the interval $1/p$ such that periodic markings of length $\text{constant}/p$ are observed, we argue, hence the i in the constraint.

As a result, a particle not only has a v (or p) vector which may be changed due to an interaction, but it also has dt_1, dx_1 values which are involved in an interaction. Both of these features appear in 2-slit interference if the slit lengths are about \hbar/p apart.

Conclusion

In conclusion, as argued in previous notes, one does not only have dx, dt such that $dx/dt=v$, but also a nature fixed dt_1, dx_1 for interactions. Both should be visible in interactions, but on classical scales only changes to v are, suggesting that dt_1 , and dx_1 are tiny in this regime. Special relativity is also velocity centric (like Newtonian mechanics) and so one might consider again that dt_1, dx_1 are always tiny and of no significance. One may obtain the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$, where t and x are intervals from $t=0, x=0$. Here it is understood that $x/t=v$ as one considers frames moving at $-v$ with respect to each other. For curiosity, one might ask about dt_1, dx_1 ? Given that $-Et+px$ is a math invariant, one should be able to use dt_1, dx_1 in the invariant. Furthermore, dt_1 and dx_1 should be independent of each other suggesting a nature imposed $dt_1=\text{constant}/E$ and $dx_1=\text{constant}/p$. If these are large with respect to system times and lengths, then dt_1 and dx_1 should be observable in an interaction just as much as v , which is the case for 2-slit interference for slit separation of about \hbar/p .